

PAGES OF THE HISTORY OF LYDOCAINE SYNTHESIS AND STUDY

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Samara State Medical University, Samara, Russia***Abstract**

The article is devoted to the history of the discovery, research and use of lidocaine, the first local anesthetic of the amide series. Historical facts, rare illustrations, biographies of chemists Nils Löfgren and Bengt Lundqvist, who contributed to the creation of one of the most effective and common local anesthetics and antiarrhythmic drugs in the world, are given.

Keywords: lidocaine, history, synthesis, Hans von Euler-Chelpin, Holger Erdtman, Nils Löfgren, Bengt Lundqvist.

Introduction.

It all started with the chemist Hans von Euler-Chelpin's interest in chemical substances in nature (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Hans Carl August Simon von Euler-Helpin (1873–1964) was a Swedish biochemist of German origin. Winner of the Nobel Prize (1929) and the German Federal Grand Cross (1959). Honorary Academician of 7 universities worldwide

In 1896, Svante Arrhenius, the coryphaeus of Swedish chemistry, persuaded him to come to Stockholm to work as a personal assistant. Von Euler-Helpin was 23 years old at the time. The focus of his scientific interests were enzymes, vitamins and the chemical secrets of genes. Euler-Helpin's book *Chemistry of Plants* (1907-1908) became a classic, as well as a source of inspiration for chemists he knew, who later pioneered new disciplines in biochemistry. He was awarded the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 1929, jointly with Sir Arthur Harden of London, for his research on yeast and fermentation. The prize was awarded for alcoholic fermentation - "the fermentation of sugars and the activity of enzymes in this process" [2].

By the turn of the twentieth century, many scientists already believed that chemical production depended on genes. Von Euler-Helpin believed that enzyme chemistry could enhance the knowledge of biology and genetics. He wanted to investigate how genes and enzymes are chemically interlinked and to record

the actual process of transmitting hereditary information in terms of chemistry. Together with Herman Nilsson-Ehle, he became interested in why certain barley species were so resistant to certain pests. In 1932, Professor Herman Nilsson-Ehle at the University of Lund offered van Uhler barley, which had undergone a mutation that rendered it incapable of producing chlorophyll. Research into the mutated barley was extended. Von Euler-Helpin divided the work between several groups of colleagues and students, Harry Hellström taking spectrometric studies of alcohol extracts from barley leaves. Using ultraviolet spectrometry, he found a component similar to indole. Closer examination led to the discovery in 1933 that this compound could be represented by the formula $C_{11}H_{14}N_2$. It proved to be a poisonous alkaloid found only in chlorophyll-deficient plants. Von Euler-Helpin gave it the name "Gramine" after the Gramine plant family. The basis of this research was the idea that the toxin could serve as an agricultural pesticide. Several other isolated studies have focused on gramine. Conclusions from old

stories about camels in Central Asia refusing to eat particular grasses were tested in Russia by Academician A.P. Orekhov and S.S. Norkina, who took up studies of various grasses. They were able to isolate the alkaloid donaxin or giant reed¹ from *Agundo donax* with a molecular formula like the indole found by von Euler-Helpin and Helström – $C_{11}H_{14}N_2$. It was identical to gramine [3; 4].

Von Euler-Helpin then took a serious interest in the exact molecular structure of gramine, which was to

be confirmed by its synthesis in the laboratory. The existing formula could be represented by at least two different isomers. The choice of an isomer for the synthesis was supported by the professor, whose evidence was decisive. From a chemical point of view, the choice was unsuccessful, which really upset von Euler-Helpin. He changed his mind when he tried to synthesise it. At this time the next important figure in the history of lidocaine is Holger Erdtman.

Fig. 2. Professor Holger Erdtman (1902–1989). When tasting the substances, he synthesised, he discovered local anaesthetic effects, which later prompted the search for new anaesthetics

Holger Erdtmann (Fig. 2) became a chemist when he was a child. At the age of 15, he took part in an investigation of a fossil settlement that was found in a peat bog. What interested him most was the acidic liquid and black soil of the peat bogs, which was quite strange.

He was fascinated by chemical processes in nature, and after reading von Euler-Helpin's *Chemistry of Plants*, he was finally and irrevocably fascinated by chemistry. Erdtman began studying chemistry under von Euler-Helpin at the Institute of General and Organic Chemistry at Stockholm University, and in 1926 obtained a licentiate degree (corresponding to a PhD), which had a clear bias towards the natural sciences - botany, chemistry and general zoology. The fascination of Erdtman's youth to study peat bog moss was still strong, and the new knowledge he acquired allowed him to delve further into his chemistry. However, he had to give up the subject for a while, because von Euler-Helpin gave him the task of writing his final thesis on renin, an important biochemical enzyme. In the process, Erdtman made a discovery that is still of importance today in understanding kidney metabolism and the vital role of calcium and magnesium ions in the

activation of renin and other enzymes. In Erdtman's time, the role of calcium in enzyme activation was undoubtedly underestimated and it was not until many years later that a detailed study of this mechanism was carried out. This work led to the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine awarded to biochemists E. Fischer and E. J. Krebs in 1992. It took almost 60 years to describe how reactions are turned on and off in body cells. Erdtman's 1928 discovery was published and used by several chemists in the 1930s and 1940s, although his own interests lay in the study of forests and marshes.

Erdtman started work on the synthesis, but did not get a gramine. Out of two possible structural formulas, the wrong one was chosen. He failed! Before he found time to try to synthesise another compound with the same molecular formula (i.e. another isomer), Theodor Wieland and Chi Yi Hsing in Germany succeeded in synthesising this substance. It was identical to gramine. This failure of Erdtman and von Euler-Helpin was turned into a success. Unlike gramine, the isogramine produced by Erdtman had the surprising property of causing numbness of the tongue and lips, which he noticed during tasting. Erdtman could have been satisfied

¹ The giant reed can grow up to 7 metres high and its trunk is used to make flutes and organ pipes as well as other wooden instruments.

with this and would not have continued further research; isogramine was toxic and the process of producing it was complicated - it could never have become a competitive painkiller.

Later, in 1971, in a letter to a colleague, Professor Bo Holmstedt, Erdtman pointed out the theoretical possibility of similar properties in intermediates produced during the synthesis, which he continued to taste in the same way as before.

"The idea was so idiotic that I checked later and found no one to suggest anything like it," Erdtman wrote.

"The main thing, however, was that this superficial idea forced me to taste the substance - with the result, familiar to everyone, of a numbing effect. Anilines of this type are technically very easy to make. I believed I had found something important and it smelled like money! I made many analogues and all of them gave a numbing effect. I sent the news to Astra. Several chemists were sent to meet me. They showed little interest but advised me to contact Ulf von Euler, which I did. The most encouraging thing was that the substance was "as good" as novocaine. Nils Löfgren then offered me his help to make similar substances. It was clear that a complete and systematic search in this field was needed. Because of the little interest shown by "Astra" and the "need for publications," the results (in a rather poorly drafted article) were published in the Swedish

magazine "Svensk Kemisk Tidskrift" (1937, vol. 48, p.163). It was a "hand of fate" that we did not have 2,6-dimethylaniline [2,6-xylidine] in the laboratory cupboard. Had we had it, we would of course have synthesised "Xylocaine" and published all the properties of this substance! Hans von Euler-Helpin lost interest in this problem when he discovered that even modified barley containing gramine could be attacked by nematode worms - and I was "temporarily dismissed".

This is Holger Erdtman's version of the development, written only 35 years later. It is probably coloured somewhat by the annoyance that Löfgren became the man who "reaped the rewards" of what he (Erdtman) "sowed". In essence, there is not much to say on the subject.

This is where Nils Löfgren comes in. It was his first introduction to the synthesis of local anaesthetics, a work which carried him away for the rest of his life.

Löfgren enrolled in the chemistry department of the Stockholm Polytechnic in 1933, and by 1935 he had co-authored (with Hellström and von Euler) a paper describing the isolation of the alkaloid gramine from mutant barley species [5]. As a student, he became an assistant lecturer at the Institute of Biochemistry, and the following year he became an assistant lecturer in the chemical laboratory run by von Euler-Helpin. It occupied the same floor as the Institute of Organic Chemistry at Kungstensgatan 45 (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The building of the Stockholm Polytechnic Institute. Built in 1904. Here, in a small windowless basement laboratory, lidocaine was synthesised

Löfgren met Erdtman. The synthesis work interested him and he offered to help Erdtman. Since they were both very interested in the relationship between molecular structure and physiological effect and Löfgren was a young and talented chemist, Erdtman

gratefully accepted the offer. The pharmaceutical company Astra provided "a small sum of money" for the work. This paid for reagents and biochemical testing for less than a year. According to eyewitness Bengt Lindberg, later a chemistry professor, Erdtman managed to get Pharmacia to give him a small research

grant because he knew the company's director. The cool attitude from Astra was probably due to the fact that the company did not think about the possibility of finding a replacement for novocaine.

When various substances were synthesised, they were subjected to a pre-test in the laboratory, which

consisted of tasting or rubbing them against the tongue. They all produced a numbing effect and were sent to Astra for further testing. The company hired Ulf von Euler, son of Hans von Euler-Helpin, as a medical consultant for this task (Fig. 4). He worked as a physiologist at the Karolinska Institute.

Fig. 4. *Ulf von Euler (1905–1983) was the first medical researcher to test the new local anaesthetic produced by Erdtman and Löfgren in the 1930s. Physiologist Ulf von Euler discovered noradrenaline and prostaglandins, and received the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1970*

Of the 16 compounds synthesised, 10 were thought to be particularly interesting. Ulf von Euler concentrated on them and tested their effects on the eyes of guinea pigs. By dropping different solutions on the cornea, he determined the strength of their local anaesthetic effect. It was measured by irritating the cornea with hairs of varying thickness, which was necessary to make the rabbit blink. Several of the formulations investigated gave a strong effect, but when Ulf von Euler compared them to novocaine, which in those years remained the best local anaesthetic, it turned out that none of them was capable of competing with it.

Erdtman and Löfgren published their results in the *Svensk Kemisk Tidskrift* (1937, vol. 49, not 48 as mentioned by Erdtman in his letter to Holmstedt). This was an important article for both chemists. Written in German, the language of chemistry at the time: *Über eine neue Gruppe von Lokalanästhetisch wirksamen Verbindungen* (On a new group of compounds with local anaesthetic effect).

After his research Holger Erdtman felt that further synthesis was not promising. Astra had not found a new substance that could compete with the anaesthetics that were already on the market and discontinued its modest financial support. Hans von Euler-Helpin lost interest as soon as it was discovered that gramine was ineffective against agricultural plant pests; furthermore, he was unwilling to personally fund research into local anaesthetics, as the problem was far removed from that which the institute had traditionally dealt with. Erdtman

has since been used by Hans von Euler-Helpin for research on a private basis. In order to earn a living, he was forced to find other work. At this time, he made one last attempt to obtain additional funding from Astra. Arriving at the company's headquarters in Södertälje without prior arrangement, he approached Arvid Ahlroth, the "plant" manager, whom he had met at a meeting of chemists in Stockholm. Ahlroth arranged with Astra president Börje Gabrielsson for a one-to-one meeting with Erdtman. As a result, a small amount of funding was given to Erdtman.

Holger Erdtman was forced to leave the chemistry department, saying later that he did so without regret because the intellectual climate was not as good as it could have been. As a supporter of the Social Democratic Party, he probably had in mind Hans von Euler-Helpin's strong pro-German attitude and his reactionary attitude to life. Erdtman himself was a staunch Anglophile and disliked von Euler-Helpin. Löfgren, on the other hand, was inclined towards socialism. At that time his views also differed from those of von Euler-Helpin. He was extremely radical and later even became a committee member of the Stockholm Radical Student Club. It is possible that Erdtman wanted to prevent Löfgren from continuing his work and convinced him that nothing more would come of the synthesis they had done together. He wrote in a letter, dated 1971, the following: "I was very upset to learn that Löfgren had continued our work with amides, as I had a steady intention of continuing the research when I got the

Hompan (Bo Holmstedt) professorship. I told Lofgren this "over a glass of grape wine". Using the same means of communication, he informed me that I didn't realise that amino acid anilide was a substance worth concentrating on (!). Löfgren eventually got a licensed degree and was "kind" enough to send me a letter saying "thank you for the idea".

Löfgren worked as a teaching assistant at the Institute of Biochemistry from 1935-1936 and later at the Institute's General Chemistry Laboratory (1936-1941). He continued his teaching activities and stopped practical work on local anaesthetics at this time [6]. In the early 1940s, Löfgren made a new attempt to resume the research he had started with Erdtmann. Between May 1940 and June 1942, Löfgren developed the local anaesthetic locastin (Lokastin), a combination of novocaine and anilines. This synthesis was actually Löfgren's first local anaesthetic to be clinically tested on patients. Toxicity and pharmacological tests were performed at the academic hospital in Uppsala by Svante Annerstam and Stig Sjölin. The anaesthetic had the advantage that it could be produced from domestic raw material but it still did not have the same effect as novocaine. It was a good alternative local anaesthetic

during the current crisis. Löfgren often thought about the problem of developing a local anaesthetic that was more effective than novocaine. The German chemists working with von Euler-Helpin probably inspired and directed his thoughts back to the synthesis of anilines in the 1930s. The basic idea during his work with Erdtman was that a local anaesthetic should have a flat molecule. Löfgren probably abandoned this idea, as Inga Fischer, one of Löfgren's students, said in 1942. He started thinking in a new direction – regarding the ortho-effect, and this eventually led to the creation of two substances that became known as LL 30 and LL 31. The substances were named after Löfgren and Lundqvist and the numbers are related to the order numbers of the synthesized prototypes [6]. As the two methyl groups occupied ortho-positions in the benzene ring, the molecule acquired a curved structure due to the distribution of the electric charge. LL 30 differed little from one of the topical formulations he had synthesized back in the 30's - only one methyl group (CH₃) was new (Fig. 5). The functional difference was significant and consisted in the spatial orientation of the molecules, which was very different.

Fig. 5. LL 30 is a sample of the new local anaesthetic lidocaine. (Ill. by K. Lindqvist, S. Sundling, 1993.)[1]

Tasting was the only method used by Löfgren to compare the potency of the drugs. The method was generally too imprecise to decide whether the new formulation was suitable as a practically applicable local anaesthetic.

The arrival of the young Bengt Lundqvist, a chemistry student, played a big role. Lundqvist introduced a new method of testing substances in chemistry, experimental injections, which were then used at Kungstensgatan 45. At this time, they did not have sufficient funds, so they could not afford to use guinea pigs, so he became their "guinea pig". Lundqvist was an ardent experimenter, full of enthusiasm for testing

various drugs on himself. Even though rabbits and guinea pigs were available, the researchers did not use them. The main reason for this was the ease of doing trials on themselves to decide how good the new drug was. They had no pharmaceutical know-how and no experience of experimentation on animals. The risk seemed minimal - at least Lundqvist was reassured.

Löfgren himself described how "Lunkan" (as everyone called Bengt Lundqvist) asked to be allowed to test the drug on himself, after which he gave him LL 30. At this time, they already had the anaesthetic (synthesised probably at the end of 1942).

Lundqvist used as a manual for his experiments a book on local anaesthesia supplied by his namesake Bengt Lagergren, a medical student, his associate and

assistant who had originally borrowed it from Dr. Torsten Gordh. Using the technique of conductive anaesthesia, he injected a drug into his finger and recorded the duration of the anaesthesia (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. *Injection into the base of the finger was the most used method of testing the local anaesthetic effect on volunteers. Pricking the needle into the fingertip allowed us to determine when anaesthesia was onset and when the effect gradually subsided*

Measured blood pressure, pulse, noted any side effects. Lundqvist injected himself in his arms, legs and body. He even included in his notes the effects of a spinal anaesthetic he gave himself in front of a mirror. Such a complicated anaesthesia in those days was only performed in hospitals which had specialists, antidotes and resuscitation equipment in case a complication arose.

It is not clear whether this is related to the experiment, but there was a case of Lundqvist failing to open the front door. He fumbled with the key, kept dropping

it and was mistaken for a drunk. It is possible that his fingers refused to obey due to the effects of local anaesthesia.

An annoyed Lundqvist disappeared from the laboratory with LL 30 and reappeared after a few days, absence, saying that it was the best local anaesthetic of all and backing up this statement with a detailed report on the research carried out. This gave Lfgren more confidence that he had finally found the substance he had been looking for (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Nils Löfgren (left) and Bengt Lundqvist. The picture was taken in the chemistry lab next to the apparatus used for the synthesis [1]. Bottom photo by AstraZeneca [26]

Researchers

Nils Löfgren and Bengt Lundqvist [6] played a major role in the history of lidocaine, of course. They worked hard to make their discovery, sacrificing a lot of themselves, patented it, and later got to enjoy their

share of the profits. They were very different people, which may be why they were so successful together from the start. When they met in 1942, Lundqvist was a young student and Löfgren a member of the department, nine years his senior. Lundqvist brought a breath

of fresh air to the stale chemistry lab. The two of them often stayed in Löfgren's office to discuss the chemical basis of local anesthesia. Löfgren had long been haunted by the idea that all local anaesthetics could be obtained from a common chemical structure. Lundqvist, on the other hand, burning with curiosity to experiment on his own body with various chemicals - was a born experimenter.

Nils Löfgren – chemist and personality

Nils Löfgren was one of the remarkable figures among Swedish research chemists – an unconventional, imaginative, capricious and sort of brilliant scientist who was also extremely meticulous and never gave up until he reached his goal. Within a few years, Löfgren was one of the richest men in Sweden - he received a large sum for synthesising lidocaine. But that money brought him more failure than happiness and, together with his addiction to alcohol and melancholy, brought him to his death at the age of 53.

He was a man of athletic build, over six feet (over 180 cm) tall. His weight ranged between 85 and 95 kg. "An extremely pleasant and energetic personality," was how he was described by Bertil Takman, a colleague and friend who had worked with him in the chemistry department since 1943. He had his own opinions on many things, often joked with others, and was a creative person who stood out in many ways with his romantic view of life. His passion for music, for example. His brother was a professional musician and his wife, Ingrid, whom he married in 1940, was the daughter of chamber orchestra musician Gustav Lagerqvist. Löfgren grew up in a musical environment, and music meant a lot to him. He once jokingly said that if you don't love Mozart and Beethoven, you will never rise in Löfgren's eyes. He was a great fan of opera and learned

to play the violin; later he kept the violin and the sheet music stand in his study. According to his friend Björn Luning, however, his musical abilities were rather modest and his playing did not improve at all over the following years. Nevertheless, he even took cello lessons later in life to improve his musical abilities.

A romantic at heart, he loved to visit the countryside and relax from his daily routine. He was also quite sporty. Claimed to have been a very good footballer in his youth. He loved ball games of all kinds, couldn't pass by kids playing football and not play a bit with them. He had a table tennis table in the house and loved to play at the first opportunity. As colleagues and family members said, physically he was very strong.

Löfgren was an extremely fair man and always tried to do right by his conscience. If he lost his temper or acted unfairly in an argument with someone, he would do everything in his power to apologize and make amends. His clothes were informal, like those of a modern university student.

Löfgren continued to work at the chemical laboratory at Kungstensgatan 45 despite his wartime service. One of his jobs was to research explosives. He also helped in the search for alternative medicines that could be made from raw materials available to Swedish pharmaceutical companies.

When the need arose to test LL 30, Löfgren asked Leonard Goldberg, MD (1911-2010) at the Karolinska Institute to analyze in detail the toxicity and effectiveness of LL 30 compared to novocaine, which was the reference local anesthetic at the time. After only two weeks of testing, he obtained preliminary data showing that LL 30 was superior to the other drugs, did not cause irritation and had low toxicity (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Leonard Goldberg in Karolinska Institutet's laboratory

Nils Löfgren successfully completed his doctorate in chemistry on 30 July 1943. He then concentrated on assisting the young colleagues in his team with their research. They, working with enthusiasm, obtained a number of excellent results on local anaesthetics, which documented their dissertations [7–9]. With the support of the firm Astra, where Löfgren worked as a scientific consultant, the financial situation improved somewhat. Despite the fame that Löfgren gained from lidocaine, he continued his teaching activities in the chemistry department until the early 50s.

Patenting of LL 30

After receiving the positive results of the LL 30 trial, Löfgren and Lundqvist quickly drafted a patent application, signed by both of them, and attached the Goldberg report to it. Lundqvist's heroic trials on himself impressed Löfgren, and he decided that he should share in the profits that could be made from the sale of lidocaine. A patent was granted on 15 July 1943. They then set to work selling the drug to a pharmaceutical company. After several companies (Pharmacia, US representative offices) refused, Astra finally got the rights to manufacture and distribute xylocaine (lidocaine) all over the world on November 22, 1943. Lidocaine brought about a real paradigm shift in anaesthesia. The drug became a money-making machine for Astra and propelled the company into the elite of the pharmaceutical industry. Dentists in Europe and the United States were the first to be introduced to the novelty, but lidocaine soon began to be used in other medical institutions in most parts of the world [26].

The researchers received 10,000 Swedish krona as a kind of "upfront payment", plus licence fees and a percentage of the profits. When marketing began, they were paid a 4% royalty on sales for 17 years. Only a few years later, when the drug was registered and released on the pharmaceutical market under the commercial name Xylocaine, did the real big money come in. Later, Löfgren was even forced to move to Switzerland to avoid too much taxation [1]. In 1948, the Food and Drug Administration approved lidocaine for use in the United States [26].

Löfgren's doctoral thesis

Before defending his doctoral thesis, Löfgren was very nervous (Fig. 9). He was especially worried about what position his opponent, the biochemist and Dr. Eric Jorpes, would take. Jorpes, who was known for his harshness, was born in Kökar, on an island belonging to Finland, and became a Swedish citizen at the age of 29. A professor at Karolinska Institutet, he gained worldwide fame for his work in purifying the anticoagulant heparin. The 54-year-old opponent was at the pinnacle of his scientific career and could have been extremely critical if he wanted to be.

Angry tongues said that in terms of chemistry, Löfgren had done little that was new since his quarrel with Erdtman in the 1930s and that, in fact, only the methyl group distinguished LL 30 from one of the formulations he had synthesised together with Erdtman.

Fig. 9.

Title page of Nils Löfgren's doctoral thesis "Research on local anaesthetics. Xylocaine, a new synthetic drug"

In his defence Löfgren convincingly demonstrated the value of xylocaine [10]. Joerpes was positive, praising the scientific quality of the thesis. However, he disapproved of the fact that the researchers were testing new local anaesthetics, recklessly performing experiments on themselves and volunteers. In addition, Jörpes

felt that Löfgren should not underestimate the importance of his work with Erdtman.

When Löfgren received the highest praise for his dissertation, he felt satisfied. This was more than 13 years after his PhD thesis at the Stockholm Polytechnic

Institute. He reached the pinnacle of his scientific career.

Problems of anaesthesiologists

In local anaesthesia with novocaine the problem was the short duration of action of the anaesthetic, the preparation for anaesthesia and the impossibility of storing the solution with a vasoconstrictor. The powder must first be diluted. Novocaine solution with adrenaline is difficult to preserve as the latter rapidly degrades in air. Adrenaline must be added to the novocaine solution in drops (which is very imprecise!) and just before the injection. Preparation for anaesthesia was therefore a lengthy process. Anaesthetists and surgeons needed an anaesthetic that was fast, effective and long lasting and could be stored in vials. At that time, lidocaine emerged to meet these requirements. In the 40s in Sweden, 1/3 of operations were performed under local anaesthesia [1; 27]. It was safer for the patients.

Fig. 10. Torsten Gordh, MD, performing his last anaesthesia before retiring as a professor at Karolinska Hospital in 1974 [11]

Here is what Gordh reported in his interview: "In the spring of 1943 we were having dinner at Stallmästaregården after a staff meeting at Karolinska Hospital. Tore Kornerup (1912–1998), who was a colleague of mine and an ophthalmologist, said he had a friend called Lundqvist with whom he had fenced and who had a new local anaesthetic. I was naturally interested, but said that before testing it, I would first like to compare its toxicity with that of the procaine we used most often. I wanted to know if it was more or less toxic before using it. It wasn't until about a year later, when I met Lundqvist and Löfgren, that I realised they really had something to offer. However, at the time I was busy with my dissertation on circulatory and respiratory disorders in ether and intravenous anaesthesia in rabbits, so I had a lot to think about.

Another person who was partly involved in the lidocaine story was Bengt Lagergréen, who was also a swordsman. He knew Lundqvist and Löfgren and when Lundqvist wanted to do some tests with finger anaesthesia, they talked to Lagergréen, who had studied with me for about 3 months in the early 1940s. I gave him a

The great risk of local anaesthesia was in interventions in areas rich in blood vessels - toxic effects on the cardiovascular and nervous systems. That is why it was important to test lidocaine for toxicity compared to novocaine.

First contact with a new local anaesthetic

This excerpt of this article is based on an interview with Torsten Gordh (1907–2010), MD, the first Swedish anaesthesiologist; Gordh was educated in Madison, Wisconsin from 1938 to 1940 by Ralph Waters (1883–1979), MD. Gordh was chief anaesthetist at Karolinska Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden, from 1940 until his retirement in 1974 (Fig. 10). Gord conducted the first clinical trials of the new local anaesthetic lidocaine (Xylocaine®; AstraZeneca, London, UK) from 1944–1947. Gordh died on 25 June 2010 at the age of 102.

book on local anaesthesia. They asked him to demonstrate finger anaesthesia because they were to make a presentation for Pharmacia in Uppsala" [11].

Deliberate overdoses

Torsten Gordh, a pioneer in Swedish anaesthesiology and the man responsible for clinical trials of xylocaine, recalls: "I induced a toxic reaction to xylocaine, which convinced me that the treatment would be the same as an overdose of novocaine. I deliberately gave patients a double dose and they would start convulsions and convulsions. But we knew how to treat that complication with barbiturates. So, the toxic reaction was reduced and all ended well. We decided that the maximum dose was one gram. The patients we studied were given three grams!

When xylocaine started to be used abroad, there were cases of toxic reactions. In this case, a 2% solution was used, whereas I was satisfied with the results of 0.25% solution administration. In my opinion, using a 2% solution was quite risky. It is only justified for dentistry where a minimum dose of 1 ml is adminis-

tered. The only problem initially experienced by dentists was the use of metal syringes. The metal particles from the syringe caused tissue irritation in patients at the injection site. In hospitals, we used glass syringes and had no such complications."

Research in Dentistry

Fig. 11. Hilding Björn (1907–1965) — Professor, Honorary Doctor of the Faculty of Dentistry at Lund University. He developed an electrical device to measure the exact depth of anaesthesia with xylocaine. His research played a major role in the development of dentistry and anaesthesia

Using an invented electrical stimulator (the prototype of today's electric odontometer), he assessed the threshold of pain sensitivity in the teeth. This was an excellent measuring technique that was well suited for testing the effectiveness of the new local anaesthetic LL 30. He created a pain model of extraordinary quality [28]. Assistant teacher Sven Huldt and his wife, Gudrun, assisted in the tests and persuaded the students to participate in the often painful, experiments. As compensation, the students received alcohol and 15 crowns a day - not a bad sum at the time.

Unfortunately, according to Goldberg, Björn wanted to publish the results in *Svensk Tandläkare Tidsskrift*, which was a "bad idea". They should have published in the *Lancet*, as Swedish dental journals were not widespread in the world. But they didn't think of that when they printed a series of 5 papers. The papers contained the main results from medical and dental research on xylocaine, and were published in 1948. Nothing had been published until then, as the patent was not ready and Löfgren prohibited any publication.

Tests on animals and several years of trials in humans showed that the drug did not irritate tissues in the

In 1944 dentists used for the first time in their practice the preparation LL 30, which later became known as xylocaine and lidocaine. Hilding Björn taught at the Royal Dental School in Stockholm (Fig. 11). His doctoral thesis was on electrostimulation of teeth.

same way as other local anaesthetics. But reports of severe swelling and irritation after anaesthesia with xylocaine began to come in from dentists. What happened? Bengt Lundqvist investigated the reports and found that the side effects were concentrated in several clinics. It turned out that some dentists were in the habit of putting local anaesthetics into their syringes in advance and then leaving the syringes ready until they were needed. In addition, their syringes were often all metal. As the xylocaine solution was more acidic than the local anaesthetics previously used, so metal ions such as copper and nickel dissolved in the syringes. After only 10-15 minutes the concentration could become so high as to cause side effects [12]. With the change to glass syringes and the change in procedures for using anaesthetics, the problem disappeared.

Biography of Nils Löfgren

Nils Magnus Löfgren (Fig. 12) was born on August 18, 1913, and grew up in Gamleby and Atvidaberg. His father Knut Hjalmar Löfgren was an accountant, married Emmy Lindberg. Nils had two older brothers and a sister.

Fig. 12. Niels Magnus Löfgren (1913–1967)

After passing his final exams at Normalm High School in Stockholm, he worked as a trainee in a pharmacy in Dalarna in 1932. He left his first job as a pharmacist and in the spring of 1933, he enrolled at the Polytechnic Institute of Stockholm (still part of Stockholm University at that time). He worked as a teaching assistant at the Institute of Biochemistry from 1935 to 1936, and at the Institute's central chemistry laboratory from 1936 to 1941. In July 1943 he was awarded his PhD degree. He successfully defended his doctoral thesis on 24 May 1948 and was appointed lecturer in chemistry on 8 June 1948. [10].

On 13 January 1956, Löfgren became Associate Professor in the Department of Organic and Biological Chemistry at the Stockholm Polytechnic Institute, and on 1 July 1963, Professor in the Department of Organic Chemistry at Stockholm University. During the next year, he left that post to pursue independent research.

Löfgren received many awards and prizes for his synthesis of lidocaine. In 1952 he was presented with the Gold Medal of the Swedish Academy of Chemistry and in 1956 with the Gold Medal of the Royal Swedish Academy of Natural Sciences (Fig. 13). In 1962 he became an honorary doctor of dentistry in Stockholm.

Fig. 13. Grand Gold Medal of the Royal Swedish Academy of Natural Sciences (left) and the first xylocaine advertisement

Nils Löfgren died in 1967. After his death, Astra established a scholarship in his name, the Nils Löfgren Scholarship, for achievements in pharmaceutical chemistry. This award is given annually to young researchers, mostly for scientific travel.

Bengt Lundqvist biography

Bengt Josef Lundqvist was born on 5 October 1922 in Stockholm (Fig. 14). He was the only child of Göta and Josef Arvid Lundqvist. His father had a manufacturing business. As a child Bengt was very fond of sports: cross-country

Fig. 14. Bengt Josef Lundqvist (1922–1953) [1]

running, swimming and shooting. He graduated from Östra Reals Gymnasium in 1941. His grades in mathematics were good, although probably not good enough to study medicine at the Karolinska Institute. He received high marks in English, mathematics and chemistry, and low marks in religious studies, drawing and French.

After leaving school, he went into military service and then went to the Stockholm Polytechnic. Fencing was a hobby that overshadowed all others in his life. His main weapon was the sabre, but he also tried his hand at foil, competing for the Swedish national team. He was a three time champion of Sweden in fencing (1948–1950). Was very interested in medicine, but

chose chemistry. He became a teaching assistant (head laboratory assistant) and took a degree in chemistry.

In 1952 Lundqvist fell down the stairs at Stockholm University at the age of 30. He suffered a severe head injury, which was followed shortly thereafter by a fatal cerebral haemorrhage in 1953. Lundqvist is buried in the Norra cemetery near Stockholm [13]. In honour

of Lundqvist's achievements, the Bengt Lundqvist Memorial Fund was established, the main purpose of which is to promote scientific research in the field of chemistry. The Swedish Chemical Society is responsible for the application and allocation of funds [14].

The importance of lidocaine in medicine

Lidocaine was the first of the amide group of drugs to be widely used in the clinic (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15. 1% lidocaine hydrochloride solution for injection, without preservatives. Illustration by J.L. Johnson

It continues to be used in medicine because of its ability to induce rapid-onset, more effective and prolonged local and regional anaesthesia, and mild allergenicity (15). Lidocaine solutions are used for infiltration anaesthesia, peripheral nerve blocks and peridural anaesthesia. In addition, a 5% solution of this drug is used for spinal anaesthesia for 30-60 minutes. Lidocaine is also used in ointments, jellies and aerosols for local anaesthesia of mucous membranes and skin (EMLA cream and patch).

Intravenous infusions of lidocaine are administered for indications not directly related to anaesthesia. This drug has been widely used in cardiology practice to treat and prevent ventricular arrhythmias (extrasystole, tachycardia, flutter, fibrillation), including in the acute period of myocardial infarction, in implantation of an artificial pacemaker, in glycoside intoxication, anaesthesia [16; 17]. In addition, intravenous lidocaine has been used to reduce high body temperature, for analgesia in chronic pain and as an adjunct to general anaesthesia. Many other amide local anaesthetics have been developed from lidocaine: mesocaine, prilocaine, mepivacaine, bupivacaine, etidocaine, articaine, EMLA, etc. [6].

In 1957, pharmacologist Bo af Eckenstam et al. [18; 26] synthesised mepivacaine and bupivacaine; in 1969, prilocaine was synthesised by Niels Löfgren and Klees Tegner [19]; and in 1972, Adams et al. [20] developed etidocaine. The first article on articaine also

appeared in 1972 [21; 22; 23]. The search by scientists continues...

Lidocaine is still the "workhorse" for local (infiltration, conduction, terminal), regional and combined anaesthesia in most outpatient clinics and hospitals worldwide. Lidocaine allows a number of operations and procedures to be performed without general anaesthesia, with excellent postoperative pain relief and reduced need for opiates and other potent drugs. Lidocaine is included by the World Health Organization in the List of Essential, Most Effective and Safe Drugs Required in Health Care [24], in Russia - in the List of Vital and Essential Drugs for Medical Use for 2019 [25]. The synthesis and introduction of lidocaine into clinical practice was a turning point in the development of local anaesthesia.

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